

SOCIAL NETWORKS AS INTEGRAL OF ICT: A PREDICTOR OF ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION

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ABSTRACT

Internet applications simultaneously are a driving force to the cultural dividend of social networks among the students of higher education. Social networks as an interactive form of networks that allow the user to with and publish to each other, generally utilizing the internet provide a ground for multiple purposes activities ranging from pleasure, business, official and academic purposes. This paper intends to discuss the other side of social networks as it influences the prediction of academic procrastination among the students of higher education. Students' tendency for irrational task delay (i.e. procrastination) may be particularly lying face down to use Internet applications simultaneously to other tasks (e.g., during homework) and in an inadequately controlled approach. It is also a review of some literature related to the topic under discussion. Issues relate to the use of social networks for other activities in the name of academics and turn to academic procrastination is common among the students of higher education. Students are more pleasure seeking than academic participation unless otherwise. Therefore, the paper suggests some techniques that low down the social networks as a predictor of academic procrastination.

Keywords: Social Networks, ICT, Academic Procrastination, Facebook, Twitter.

INTRODUCTION

The Internet has rapidly evolved from being merely an information-sharing platform to being a social networking platform used by individuals to share content, opinions, and information. Social networking is a global phenomenon that has revolutionized how people interact with each other. It affects nearly every aspect of our life: education, communication, employment, politics, healthcare, social relationships, and personal productivity (Liu & Ying, 2012; Bacik, 2016; Suleiman, Muhammad, et al, 2020; Awobamise & Jarrar, 2019; Okiyi et al, 2019; Awobamise, 2018).

A social networking service (SNS) is an Internet-based platform used in building and developing social relations among people. It provides means by which users can

interact online with people of similar interests, whether it be for romantic or social purposes. It allows users to share emails, instant messaging, online comments, wikis, digital photos, and videos, and post blog entries. It also offers people with disabilities a chance to make their thoughts and opinions known in a virtual environment (Liu & Ying, 2012; Bacik, 2016). Social networking has become one of the most important communication tools among people nowadays (Awobamise & Jarrar, 2019; Awobamise, 2015). However, social networks exist on the Internet websites where millions of people share interests on certain disciplines, make available to members of these networks various shared files and photos, and videos, create blogs and send messages, and conduct real-time conversations. These networks are described as social because they allow communication with friends and colleagues to study and strengthen the ties between members of these networks in the space of the Internet.

The most famous in the world of social networks are Facebook (Facebook.com) and Twitter (Twitter.com) and MySpace (myspace.com) and others (Jalal and Zaidieh 2012). Electronic social-networking services such as MySpace and especially Facebook have rapidly earned fame. The model of the web as a decentralized search engine to search for information or communicate with others is becoming obsolete (Jalal & Zaidieh, 2012; Suleiman et al. 2020).

Social networks serve dual roles as both the suppliers and the consumers of content. They provide the user with a choice of who can view their profile. A profile is generated from answers to questions, such as age, location, interests, etc. Some sites allow users to upload pictures, add multimedia content, or modify the look and feel of the profile, post blogs, comment on postings, compile and share a list of contacts. To protect user privacy, social networks typically have controls that allow users to choose who can view their profile, contact them, add them to their list of contacts, and so on (Bacik 2016).

Human asset quality improvement is required as restoration endeavors in the field of training. One of the necessary reestablishments is to set up the understudies to turn into a long-life student. The need to get ready understudies to turn into a long-life student is basic since, right now, the world is loaded with vulnerability and quick changes. In such conditions, a person who can turn into a long-life student will figure out how to conform to the vulnerability and fast changes. It is quite certain that social networking and ICT for academic transformation are effectively been utilized by the students, teachers, and researchers nowadays as the rings of globalization. A social network is a family member of ICT in many dimensions especially interns of the usage for academic purposes, communication, and another aspect of human endeavor (Sani Shitu 2019).

Taking the nature and services of social networking and ICT in the field of media technology, the two concepts can hardly be separated they are integrated especially when considering the role of each in the area of communication and networking with regard field of education, and this may entail the prediction of students' academic procrastination. Let us see the issues related to each, social networking allows users

to share ideas, digital photos and videos, posts, and to inform others about online or real-world activities and events with people in their network. The web enables people to connect with others who live in different locations, ranging from across a city to across the world. Depending on the social networking platform, members may be able to contact any other member. In other cases, members can get in touch with anyone they have a connection to, and afterward anyone that contacts have a connection to, and so on (Sani, 2019).

The success of social networking services can be identified in the supremacy of society today, with Facebook having a massive 2.13 billion active monthly users and an average of 1.4 billion daily active users in 2017. LinkedIn, a career-oriented social-networking service, generally requires that a member personally know another member in real life before contacting him or her online. Some services require members to have a preexisting connection to contact other members. Many schools, colleges & universities have begun the facility of interconnecting with a large number of students through the means of social networks, for example, Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube.

While the term ICT is, also use to refer to the convergence of audiovisual and telephone networks with computer networks through a single cabling or link system. There are large economic incentives to merge the telephone network with the computer network system using a single unified system of cabling, signal distribution, and management. ICT is an umbrella term that includes any communication device, encompassing radio, television, cell phones, computer and network hardware, satellite systems and so on, as well as the various services and appliance with them such as video conferencing and distance learning. Therefore, it is clear now that social networking is an integral part of ICT, and ICT plays the roles of providing good services to humanities including educational services at various levels may predict the source of students' academic procrastination. Students engaged too much on ICT activities other than academics might be at the risk of been procrastinated and subsequently resulted in low performance despite the educational advantages of ICT (Sani, 2019).

Social networking had also contributed to the acceleration of the production and dissemination of knowledge and information. Other technologies are now pushing innovations further such as robotics, artificial intelligence, etc., along with the creation of new globalization. Sharing of information, links to other sites has now become super easy for students as they share pieces of information with their friends, classmates, and other connections. Therefore, the contribution of social networking to the student of higher learning is immeasurable in all most every nook and corner ranging from day one of entering the institution through registration, teaching-learning process techniques to the graduation of students. It is only the addiction of social networking by the students may turn to the improper utilization of social networking from academic to other things else and a such may cause academic procrastination subsequently extended to the students' academic performance (Liu & Ying, 2012; Suleiman et al. 2020).

It is believed that obsession with social networking is higher in people with anxiety, stress, depression, and low self-esteem. Students are one of the most important users of the virtual world and social networks. The overuse of social networks has negative impacts on academic, social, and health consequences for the students. Reduced academic performance is one of the most important consequences of social networking overuse for students. The results of a study on medical students showed that students who used social networks and the internet more than average had poor academic achievement and a low level of concentration in the classroom. Social networks site addiction had the greatest impact and correlation with academic procrastination among school students of higher education (Liu & Ying, 2012; Suleiman et al. 2020).

What is ICT?

ICT is a truncation that means "Information and Communication Technologies". ICTs are an umbrella term that incorporates all innovations for the control and communication of all digital information. ICT considers all the vocations of computerized development that as of now exists to help people, business, and institutions. It is difficult to portray ICT because it is difficult to keep up the movements they occur so rapidly. ICT is a worry with the limit, recovery, control, transmission of computerized information. The ICTs can be described as the processing and communication agencies and highlights that differently bolster instructing, learning, and scope of exercises in education (Suleiman et al, 2020)

Social Networks and Social Networking Sites

Social network sites are those web-based services that allow individuals to (1) construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, (2) articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection, and (3) view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system. What makes social network sites unique is not that they allow individuals to meet strangers, but rather that they enable users to articulate and make visible their social networks. These meetings are frequently between "latent ties" (Liu and Ying 2012) who share some offline connection. On many of the large social network sites, participants are not necessarily looking to meet new people; instead, they are primarily communicating with people who are already a part of their extended social network (Liu & Ying 2012).

The backbone of social network sites consists of visible profiles that display an articulated list of friends who are also users of the system. Profiles are unique pages where one can "type oneself into being" (Liu & Ying 2012). After joining social network sites, an individual is asked to fill out forms containing a series of questions with which the profile is generated. Typically, a profile includes descriptors such as age, location, interests, an "about me" section, and an uploading photo. After joining a social network site, users are prompted to identify others in the system with whom they have a relationship. These relationships differ by using different labels such as "Friends", "Contacts", and "Fans". Social network sites use two kinds of confirmation

for friendship. One is one-directional ties sometimes labeled as "Fans" or "Followers," though many sites call these Friends as well. The other is bi-directional confirmation, which needs both sides to agree on the friendship. The public display of connections is a crucial component of social network sites. The friends' list contains links to each friend's profile, enabling viewers to traverse the network graph by clicking through the friend lists. Most social network sites also provide a mechanism for users to leave messages on their Friends' profiles. This feature typically involves leaving "comments". Besides, social network sites often have a private messaging feature similar to webmail (Liu & Ying 2012).

Benefits of Social Networking Sites

Worldwide Connectivity: No matter if you are searching for that former college roommate, your first-grade teacher, or an international friend, there is no easier or faster way to make a connection than via the social network. Although Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and MySpace are probably the most well-known social networking communities, new websites are popping up regularly that are dedicated to allowing people to connect and to interact via the Internet. Through such sites, individuals make new friends or business connections or extend their base by connecting and interacting with friends of friends and so forth (Jadoon n.d.; Jarrar, et al. 2020).

The commonality of Interest: When you opt to participate in a social network community, you can choose those individuals whose likes and dislikes are similar to yours and build your network around those commonalities. For instance, if you are a chess aficionado or a book lover, you can find and interact with those who share your interest. Because you are connecting digitally instead of having to physically attend meetings, you have the luxury of joining many more groups and communities. You can meet with your friends anytime you have an Internet connection and whenever you find them online (Jadoon n.d.).

Real-Time Information Sharing: Many social networking sites incorporate an instant messaging feature, which means you can exchange information in real-time via a chat. This is a great feature for teachers to use to facilitate classroom discussions. A study by the John D. and Catherine T. MacArthur Foundation shows these networks can be used as effective vehicles for students to pursue self-paced online learning. Besides, the Internet is the ultimate online textbook. Students no longer need to take out six library books at a time. Much of what they need to know they can find online (Jadoon n.d.), (Suleiman et al. 2020).

Free Advertising: Whether you are a non-profit organization that needs to get the word out about your upcoming fundraiser or a business owner marketing a new product or service, there's no better way to get your message in front of millions of people 24/7. The best part is it that you can spread the word through social networking profiles for free. You can promote one product, service, or idea, or many because you are limited only by the amount of time you wish to invest in the endeavor (Jadoon n.d.).

Increased News Cycle Speed: Social networking has revolutionized the speed of the news cycle. Many news organizations now collaborate with social networking sites like Twitter, YouTube, and Facebook to both collect and share information. One can get a sense of what is going on in the world just by watching trending topics from many of these sites. This has led to the development of a nearly instantaneous news cycle as millions of social networking updates rapidly spread news and information (Jadoon n.d.).

Challenges of Social Networking Sites

Many challenges are facing the use of social networking in education such as privacy, taking up time, and miscommunication (Jalal & Zaidieh, 2012).

Face-to-Face Connections are endangered: A huge advantage of these social communities has a reverse side effect that is also a big disadvantage of social networking: they reduce or eliminate face-to-face socialization. Because of the autonomy afforded by the virtual world, individuals are free to create a fantasy persona and can pretend to be someone else (Jadoon n.d.; Jalal & Zaidieh 2012).

Cyberbullying and Crimes against Children: Use of social networks can expose individuals to harassment or inappropriate contact from others. Unless parents are diligent to filter the Internet content to which their families are exposed, children could be exposed to pornography or other inappropriate content (Jadoon n.d.; Jalal & Zaidieh, 2012; Suleiman et al. 2020).

The Pew Center, in their Cyberbullying 2010 report, states that 93 percent of teens aged 12 to 17 use the Internet. Of that 93 percent, 63 percent of them use the Internet daily. Such high usage increases the risk of their being victims of cyberbullying or other cybercrimes (Jadoon n.d.; Jalal & Zaidieh 2012).

Risks of Fraud or Identity Theft: Whether you like it or not, the information you post on the Internet is available to almost anyone clever enough to access it. Most thieves need just a few vital pieces of personal information to make your life a nightmare and if they successfully steal your identity, it could cost you dearly. A report on CNET reveals over 24 million Americans put their personal information at risk by posting it on public sites such as social communities (Jadoon n.d.; Jalal & Zaidieh, 2012; Suleiman et al. 2020).

Time Waster: A Nielsen report explains that social networking can be a big waste of time that sucks 17 percent of our Internet time down the non-productivity drain. While it is true that some of that time is likely spent in making and maintaining important business, social or professional connections, it is also true that it is easy to become distracted and end up spending valuable time on games, chats, or other non-related activities. Dorie Clark of the Huffington Post reports Facebook users to spend about six hours each month on the site, while social networkers spend three times as much time on those communities as they do on other online activities like email (Jadoon n.d.; Jalal & Zaidieh 2012).

Corporate Invasion of Privacy: Social networking invites major corporations to invade your privacy and sell your personal information. Have you ever posted a comment on Facebook, only to notice an advertisement appear with content related to your post? Facebook projects it will earn \$3.8 billion in revenue in 2011. That is not bad for a free site. If Facebook and other social networking sites do not charge their members, however, how do they make so much money? They do it by selling the ability to specifically target advertisements. On social networking sites, the website is not the product, its users are. These sites run algorithms that search for keywords, web browsing habits, and other data stored on your computer or social networking profile and provide you with advertisements targeted specifically to you. At the same time, you may be giving the site permission to share your information with outside sources unless you specifically generate settings that disallow them to do so. Participating in applications like Farmville may also be allowing outside vendors access to your private information (Jadoon n.d.; Aggarwal, 2019; Jalal & Zaidieh 2012).

Test anxiety

Test anxiety may be defined as nervousness which subjectively relates to tests and their penalty, being afraid of failing a test, and of the cost of failing, is at the heart of this ill-feeling that test anxiety can be experienced, both before and during the taking of a test. Seen from the viewpoint of trait-state conceptions of anxiety, such anxiety is a state emotion when it relates to a specified test and is experienced before or during that test. As it is experienced habitually over extended periods and for dispositional reasons, test anxiety is a situation-specific type of trait anxiety. Test anxiety is often present during the preparatory period may employ avoidance behaviors to decrease anxiety in preparing for examinations (Poorman et al., 2011; Sani, 2019).

Predictor

A predictor is a person or thing that predicts that something will happen in the future or will be a consequence of something. "Business trend predictors have said some interesting things about the power of networks" Mia is a psychologist who is interested in developing a program for first-generation college students. ... In this example, attendance is the predictor variable. A predictor variable is a variable that is being used to predict some other variable or outcome (Sani, 2019).

Procrastination

Procrastination involves avoiding doing what we know we should be doing. Sometimes we can be creative in our avoidance strategies. The best definition for procrastination is the delaying of a task that was originally planned despite expecting to be worse off the delay (Van Eerde, 2003). It is evident that all conceptualizations of procrastination recognize that there must be a postponing, delaying, or putting off a task or decision, in keeping with the term's Latin origins of pro meaning "forward, forth, or in favor of, 'and castings, meaning "of tomorrow" (Beniwal 2019). Procrastination also is the deferment or avoidance, without good reason, of an

intended or scheduled task until later. The word has its origins in Latin: pro- (forward) and crustiness (of tomorrow) (Service n.d.).

Academic Procrastination

In an academic context, it appears to affect a great number of students. Self-reporting by students suggest that 80-95 percent engage in procrastination of some sort (Ellis & Knaus, 1977; O'Brien, 2002), and almost 50 percent procrastinate consistently, which leads to problems with assignments or other set tasks (Day, Mensink, & O'Sullivan, 2000; Haycock, 1993; Onwuegbuzie, 2000 Cited in Service n.d.; Sani, 2019).

Procrastination is the practice of carrying out less urgent tasks in preference to more urgent ones, or doing more pleasurable things in place of less pleasurable ones, and thus putting off impending tasks to a later time. For a behavior to be classified as procrastination: it must be counterproductive, needless, and delaying. Similarly, it is to voluntarily delay an intended course of action despite expecting to be worse off for the delay. It is the application of procrastination to the field of education that makes academic procrastination, which refers to the delay of academic activities. Although there is no universally accepted definition, academic procrastination can be defined as the postponement of academic goals to the point where optimal performance becomes highly unlikely, resulting in a state of psychological distress (Service n.d.; Beniwal, 2019).

Research by (Schwartz 2010) clearly stated that posited academic procrastination can also be implied as perceiving that an individual, should, and somewhat intends to prepare before an examination but the thought, may cause feelings of frustration, fear, and apprehension (Edelman & Ficorelli, 2005). Due to these unpleasant feelings, undergraduate students may tend to procrastinate.

Characteristics

The Procrastinator is often remarkably optimistic about his ability to complete a task on a tight deadline; this is usually accompanied by expressions of reassurance that everything is under control. Therefore, there is no need to start. For example, he may estimate that a paper will take only five days to write; he has fifteen days there is plenty of time; no need to start now. There is enough time. At this point, considerable effort is directed towards completing the task, and work progresses. This sudden leaping of energy is the source of the inaccurate feeling that "I only work well under pressure." Actually, at this point, you are making progress only because you have not any choice. Your back is against the wall and there are no alternatives. Progress is being made, but you have lost your freedom. Procrastination continuously makes you unproductive (Beniwal, 2019). A procrastinator person has the following characters: -

- a. Procrastinators are late. Procrastinators find it hard to start working on something.

- b. Procrastinators always complain about how hard things are and how busy they are.
- c. Procrastinators do not have systems that mean no proper planning to accomplish a task.
- d. Procrastinators usually do not finish what they start. Procrastinators do not prioritize tasks, which is important for them and which is not.
- e. Procrastinators have too many things on their mind and their commotion list.
- f. Procrastinators often forget every important thing.
- g. Procrastinators check social networks, emails constantly, and most often there's nothing new to see (Beniwal 2019).

Causes of Academic procrastination

The causes of procrastination are complex and as yet far from being fully understood. However, a recent paper by Steele (2007) summarized his review of several hundred academic studies of procrastination, dating from the 1930s onwards, in an attempt to identify the cause, effect, and possible remedies for it. There appear to be four factors at work relating to:

- a. The proneness of person to procrastination.
- b. Time available to do the set task.
- c. Importance or value of set task to an individual.
- d. Desirability, or attractiveness, of the set task to an individual.

Types of procrastination

Fundamentally, there are two fundamental kinds of procrastination: The tense and the relaxed. The tense afraid type of procrastinator is described as feeling overwhelmed by pressures, unrealistic about time, uncertain about goals, dissatisfied with accomplishments, indecisive, blaming others, or other circumstances for his/her failures, lacking in confidence, and, sometimes perfectionist. This type thinks what he determines his /her work/she does, which reflects his/her level of ability. He is afraid of being judged and found wanting. Thus, this kind of procrastinator will be over-stressed and overworked until he escapes the pressure temporarily by trying to relax but any enjoyment gives rise to guilt and more apprehension. The various tense types for afraid of procrastinator comes in five forms, as described by (Beswick, et al., 1988; Beniwal, 2019).

Procrastination research is a new field for researchers, but researches have started to describe different types of procrastination among school settings. To evaluate all these, there are two types of procrastination; those are particularly common during research work, which is as follows:

- 1) Those who are fearful of success in school;
- 2) Those who are afraid of failing;
- 3)

Those who need to feel in control and to resist the control of someone else refer to this type as the "angry defiant procrastinator"; 4) Those who procrastinate to keep someone they need close to them, and 5) Those who tend to keep a frightening relationship at a distance. (Pychyl et al., 2000) have also classified procrastinators into different types: the "perfectionist" who dreads doing anything less than perfect, the "dreamer" who has great ideas but hates doing the details, the "worrier" who doesn't think things are right but fears that changes will make them worse, the "definer" who resists doing anything suggested or expected by someone else, The "crisis-maker" who manages to find or make a big problem in any project (often by starting too late), and the "over-doer" who takes on way too many tasks (Beniwal, 2019).

The second type of procrastinator is the relaxed pleasure-seeking procrastinator, who found this type to be much more common among college students than the tense-afraid type. Beswick et al. (1988) call this the easily frustrated, self-indulgent procrastinator. The relaxed procrastinator's thoughts may push him/her away from his work or studies. To such a person gain is not worth the pain, especially since the necessary work seen by them as so distasteful, boring, or stupid that they just cannot do it (Sani, 2019).

Hiomura et al. (Cited in Sani, 2019) have distinguished two different types of procrastinators: passive versus active procrastinators. Cognitively, passive procrastinators do not intend to procrastinate, but they often end up postponing tasks because of their inability to make decisions quickly and thereby act on them quickly whereas active procrastinators are capable of acting on their decisions promptly, however. They suspend their actions deliberately and focus their attention on other important tasks. Effectively, when a deadline approaches passive procrastinators to feel pressured and become pessimistic in their outlook, especially about their ability to achieve satisfactory results (Ferrari et al. 1992). Their thought of self-doubt and inadequacy increases the chance of failure and induce feelings of guilt and depression (Steel et al, 2001). Active procrastinators on the other hand, like to work under pressure. When faced with last-minute tasks they feel challenged and motivated and that feeling immunizes them against the kind of suffering common in passive procrastinators.

In the proceeding, an attempt has been made to clarify the concept of procrastination. Procrastination has been with us, as a race, since at least the birth of civilization. The investigator has studied general as well as academic procrastination as given which is relatively concerned with undergraduate students of any level (Sani, 2019).

CONCLUSION

It is believed that social networking is part of ICT in terms of their services to humanities students inclusive. We cannot underestimate the contributions of social networks and ICT to the globalization of the day, especially in the education field of

endeavor but there is need to provide the policy that helps in regulating the affairs, by educational administrators and another stakeholder to reduce the level of students' academic procrastination. Students engaged in social networking on other things than academic procrastinated academically. Therefore, it will be good if the institutions provide the policy regarding the students' network addiction.

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